

NUMERICAL ANALYSIS OF MICRO-MACRO COUPLED BEHAVIORS FOR FIBROUS COMPOSITES UNDER LARGE DEFORMATION

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SUMMARY: In this paper we present the numerical analysis of micro-macro coupled behavior for fibrous composite under large deformation. First we discuss on the periodicity of composite material after large deformation by the tensile test of knitted fabric composite material. Next the formulation of the homogenization method applied to large deformation problem is described. In this formulation, assuming that the macroscopic deformation is uniform and consequently the microstructures are periodically arrayed, the microscopic deformation is precisely defined by the perturbed displacement and product of macroscopic displacement gradient and microscopic coordinates. Using the computer program developed on the basic of this formulation, the analysis of large deformation of the unidirectional fiber reinforced composite material is carried out.

KEYWORDS: Simulation, Micro-macro, Homogenization, Large Deformation, FRP.

INTRODUCTION

In recent years, the composite materials are used in many engineering fields. The macroscopic characteristics of the composite materials depend on the microstructure and the properties of fiber and matrix. Thus, micro-macro coupled problems are becoming an important issue in such fields as applied mathematics, applied mechanics and computational mechanics. The methods like a RVE method [1] to calculate equivalent macroscopic properties of composite material have been developed. Especially, because of the insufficiency in their description of the boundary conditions, the homogenization method is a matter of concern not only in the computational mechanics field but also in the materials science field.

The basic theory of the homogenization method can be found in the papers published in 1970's and early 1980's by many applied mathematicians [2-6]. Guedes and Kikuchi [7] has developed a new formulation of this method in a weak form and shown a guideline for numerical analysis

to engineers. Then the challenge to extend the homogenization method to solve various nonlinear problems has been carried out in 1990's [8-13]. However, the application of this method to large deformation problem has been remained as open problem up to now. We can find only few literatures on the large deformation analysis by the homogenization method, for instance, papers [14-15] by Terada et al. and one [16] by Okada et al. But they didn't define the microscopic deformation. That's why, the update of the microstructure under large deformation was not clearly discussed.

Therefore, we present a new formulation of the homogenization method for large deformation analysis of composite materials with clear definition of the microscopic deformation. Using a computer program developed on the basis of this formulation, we analyze the mechanical behaviors of unidirectional fiber reinforced composite materials under large deformation.

DISCUSSION ON THE PERIODICITY AFTER LARGE DEFORMATION

The research works on the forming processes have been carried out such as the deep-draw forming process of knitted fabric composite thermoplastics investigated by Nishiyabu [17]. In such forming process, large deformation occurs both macroscopically and microscopically. In such case, the problem in the application of the homogenization method is whether the assumption of the periodicity is true or not. In fact, Okada et al. [16] formulated the homogenization method considering rigorous satisfaction of the periodicity. Therefore, the microstructural large deformation of knitted fabric composite material under uni-axial tension at high temperature was investigated experimentally. The microstructure was observed by CCD camera. The dimension of a microscopic unit cell has the order of 1-2 mm, which is illustrated in Fig.1. In this study, knitted fabrics made of aramid fibers and polypropylene were used. Because the used polypropylene is black colored, white marks were written at the cross points of knitted fabrics so as to trace the large deformation of the microstructures as shown in Fig.2. When this

Fig. 1: Unit cell of knitted fabrics

Undeformed

Largely deformed

Tensile load

Fig.2 Experimental investigation on the periodicity of the microstructure after large deformation

composite material was stretched at 443K, because polypropylene is one of the thermoplastics and also because knitted architecture allows flexible deformation, both the global structure and microstructure were largely deformed as shown in Fig.2.

From this experiment, it was found that the assumption of periodicity holds before deformation for knitted fabric composites. Moreover, the periodicity locally remains even after the large deformation. In other words, although we can see many differently deformed microstructures place by place in the largely deformed specimen, the periodicity can be satisfied locally and microscopically. This experimental fact validates our assumption that is illustrated in Fig.3. In this problem setting, the homogenization method is applicable to large deformation problems similarly to the conventional applications to linear problems.

Fig.3: Macroscopic uniform deformation and the assumption of the periodicity of microstructures

FORMULATION

Assume that a three-dimensional elastic body is the assembly of periodic microscopic structures. Now, we consider two coordinate systems, i.e., macroscopic coordinate system \mathbf{X} and microscopic one \mathbf{Y} , which are related by the scale ratio ε as follows.

$$\mathbf{y} = \mathbf{x} / \varepsilon \quad (1)$$

$\mathbf{x} = (x_1, x_2, x_3)$ is written in the macroscopic coordinate system \mathbf{X} , and $\mathbf{y} = (y_1, y_2, y_3)$ is written in microscopic one \mathbf{Y} . \mathbf{X} is used to describe the global structure, while \mathbf{Y} is used to describe the microstructure. Because we assume that the microstructure is very small compared with the global structure, the scale ratio ε is a very small number.

We assume that the macroscopic deformation is uniform, i.e., the distribution of macroscopic strain and stress are uniform as shown in Fig.3. However, if we consider the effects of the microstructure, the displacement is resolved into the uniform displacement $u_i^0(\mathbf{x})$ and the perturbed term $u_i^1(\mathbf{x})$ caused by the microscopic heterogeneity. Now both of these two displacements are written in \mathbf{X} -coordinate system. Unlike what have been assumed in other research works, $u_i^1(\mathbf{x})$ is not the displacement of microstructure. When we consider the order of the scale ratio ε , u_i^1 described in the coordinate system \mathbf{X} is very small. Therefore, the formulation of resolution of displacement could be rewritten as Eqn 1 using the coordinate system \mathbf{Y} as well as \mathbf{X} .

$$u_i^\varepsilon = u_i^0(\mathbf{x}) + \varepsilon u_i^1(\mathbf{y}) \quad (2)$$

By magnifying the microscopic model with the scale ratio ε , it becomes of the same size as the macroscopic model. Still $u_i^1(\mathbf{y})$ is not the displacement of microstructure. The displacement of macroscopic model written in the coordinate system \mathbf{X} and the displacement of microscopic model written in the coordinate system \mathbf{Y} are defined by the following equation.

$$U_i^{macro} = u_i^\varepsilon(\mathbf{x}) \quad (3)$$

$$U_i^{micro} = u_i^\varepsilon(\mathbf{y}) \quad (4)$$

By using Eqn 2 and knowing that ε is very small, we can write as follows.

$$U_i^{macro} = u_i^\varepsilon(\mathbf{x}) \cong u_i^0(\mathbf{x}) \quad (5)$$

When applying the macroscopic uniform deformation on the model, the displacement $u_i^0(\mathbf{x})$ written in the coordinate system X is described by using constant α_{ij} as follows.

$$u_i^0(\mathbf{x}) = \alpha_{ij}x_j + u_i^0(0) \quad \Rightarrow \quad \alpha_{ij} = \frac{\partial u_i^0(\mathbf{x})}{\partial x_j} \quad (6)$$

where $u_i^0(0)$ is the displacement at the origin of the macroscopic coordinate system X (the value is described in the macroscopic coordinate system).

By multiplying the both sides of Eqn 1 by α_{ij} and considering the difference of origins of both coordinate systems X and Y, we obtain the next relation.

$$\alpha_{ij}(x_j - x_j^{y=0}) = \varepsilon\alpha_{ij}y_j \quad (7)$$

where $x_j^{y=0}$ is the position of the origin of the microscopic coordinate system Y written in the macroscopic coordinate system X. When the origin of macroscopic coordinate system is equal to that of microscopic coordinate system, $x_j^{y=0}$ is equal to zero. From above equations, Eqn 6 can be written in the following way.

$$u_i^0(\mathbf{x}) = \varepsilon\alpha_{ij}y_j + \alpha_{ij}x_j^{y=0} + u_i^0(0) \quad (8)$$

If we consider only the deformation of the microstructure after the macroscopic uniform deformation, the displacement of the origin of the microscopic coordinate system Y is zero. Consequently, Eqn 8 yields the next equation.

$$u_i^0(\mathbf{x}) = \varepsilon\alpha_{ij}y_j \quad (9)$$

Based on these equations, the displacement of microstructure can be written in the coordinate system Y as follows.

$$U_i^{micro}(\mathbf{y}) = \frac{\partial u_i^0(\mathbf{x})}{\partial X_j} y_j + u_i^1(\mathbf{y}) \quad (10)$$

The first term of Eqn 10 is the value of coordinates in microscopic coordinate system multiplied by the macroscopic displacement gradient, which expresses the macroscopic uniform deformation. The rate of the Green-Lagrange strains in macro- and microscopic models are defined by Eqs 11 and 12. To obtain these equations, we used Eqs 3 and 10, and also used the updated-Lagrangian formulation. The quadratic term of the strain rate was supposed to be

negligible. Eqn 13 denotes the second Piola-Kirchhoff stress in the microstructure. The second Piola-Kirchhoff stress in global structure is defined later.

$$\dot{E}_{ij}^{macro}(\mathbf{x}) = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial \dot{U}_i^{macro}(\mathbf{x})}{\partial X_j} + \frac{\partial \dot{U}_j^{macro}(\mathbf{x})}{\partial X_i} \right) = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial \dot{u}_i^0(\mathbf{x})}{\partial X_j} + \frac{\partial \dot{u}_j^0(\mathbf{x})}{\partial X_i} \right) \quad (11)$$

$$\dot{E}_{ij}^{micro}(\mathbf{y}) = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial \dot{U}_i^{micro}(\mathbf{y})}{\partial Y_j} + \frac{\partial \dot{U}_j^{micro}(\mathbf{y})}{\partial Y_i} \right) = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial \dot{u}_i^0(\mathbf{x})}{\partial X_j} + \frac{\partial \dot{u}_j^0(\mathbf{x})}{\partial X_i} + \frac{\partial \dot{u}_i^1(\mathbf{y})}{\partial Y_j} + \frac{\partial \dot{u}_j^1(\mathbf{y})}{\partial Y_i} \right) \quad (12)$$

$$\dot{S}_{ij}^{micro} = C_{ijkl}^\varepsilon \dot{E}_{kl}^{micro} \quad (13)$$

The governing equation of large deformation theory is given as Eqn 14. This equation is obtained by substituting the constitutive equation between the second Piola-Kirchhoff stress and Green-Lagrange strain to the principle equation of virtual work expressed in rate form and by applying the updated-Lagrangian formulation.

$$\int_{\Omega} \frac{\partial \delta u_i}{\partial X_j} (C_{ijkl}^\varepsilon + \delta_{ik} S_{jl}) \frac{\partial \dot{u}_k}{\partial X_\ell} d\Omega = \int_{\Omega} \delta u_i \dot{b}_i d\Omega + \int_{\Gamma} \delta u_i \dot{t}_i d\Gamma \quad (14)$$

From Eqs 2 and 14, we can write the next equation.

$$\begin{aligned} \int_{\Omega} \frac{\partial \delta(u_i^0(\mathbf{x}) + \varepsilon u_i^1(\mathbf{y}))}{\partial X_j} (C_{ijkl}^\varepsilon + \delta_{ik} S_{jl}) \frac{\partial \delta(u_k^0(\mathbf{x}) + \varepsilon u_k^1(\mathbf{y}))}{\partial X_\ell} d\Omega \\ = \int_{\Omega} \delta(u_i^0(\mathbf{x}) + \varepsilon u_i^1(\mathbf{y})) \dot{b}_i d\Omega + \int_{\Gamma} \delta(u_i^0(\mathbf{x}) + \varepsilon u_i^1(\mathbf{y})) \dot{t}_i d\Gamma \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

Using the averaging principle with taking the limit of $\varepsilon \rightarrow 0$, Eqn 15 can be separated into two equations. Then assuming the following relation, the rate of the macroscopic uniform displacement gradient bridges the gap between the macroscopic scale and microscopic scale.

$$u_i^1(\mathbf{y}) = -\chi_i^{k\ell}(\mathbf{y}) \frac{\partial \dot{u}_k^0(\mathbf{x})}{\partial X_\ell} \quad (16)$$

Finally, the two following solvable equations are obtained.

$$\int_{\Omega} \frac{\partial \delta u_i^1(\mathbf{y})}{\partial Y_j} (C_{ijmn}^\varepsilon + \delta_{im} S_{jn}) \frac{\partial \chi_m^{k\ell}(\mathbf{y})}{\partial Y_n} d\Omega = \int_{\Omega} \frac{\partial \delta u_i^1(\mathbf{y})}{\partial Y_j} (C_{ijkl}^\varepsilon + \delta_{ik} S_{jl}) d\Omega \quad (17)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \int_{\Omega} \frac{\partial \delta u_i^0(\mathbf{x})}{\partial X_j} \frac{\partial \dot{u}_k^0(\mathbf{x})}{\partial X_\ell} \frac{1}{|Y|} \int_Y \left((C_{ijkl}^\varepsilon + \delta_{ik} S_{jl}) + (C_{ijmn}^\varepsilon + \delta_{im} S_{jn}) \frac{\partial \chi_m^{k\ell}(\mathbf{y})}{\partial Y_n} \right) dY d\Omega \\ = \int_{\Omega} \delta u_i^0(\mathbf{x}) \dot{b}_i d\Omega + \int_{\Gamma} \delta u_i^0(\mathbf{x}) \dot{t}_i d\Gamma \end{aligned} \quad (18)$$

$\chi_m^{k\ell}(\mathbf{y})$ is the characteristic displacement, which is the solution of microscopic Eqn 17. There are 9 modes of characteristic displacements because Eqn 17 tells the asymmetry w.r.t. k and ℓ . Define the homogenized coefficients as follows.

$$C_{ijkl}^H = \frac{1}{|Y|} \int_Y \left((C_{ijkl}^\varepsilon + \delta_{ik} S_{j\ell}) + (C_{ijmn}^\varepsilon + \delta_{im} S_{jn}) \frac{\partial \chi_m^{k\ell}(\mathbf{y})}{\partial Y_n} \right) dY \quad (19)$$

Then, macroscopic equation (18) can be simplified as follows.

$$\int_{\Omega} \frac{\partial \delta u_i^0(\mathbf{x})}{\partial X_j} \frac{\partial \dot{u}_k^0(\mathbf{x})}{\partial X_\ell} C_{ijkl}^H d\Omega = \int_{\Omega} \delta u_i^0(\mathbf{x}) \dot{b}_i d\Omega + \int_{\Gamma} \delta u_i^0(\mathbf{x}) \dot{t}_i d\Gamma \quad (20)$$

By solving Eqn 20, the rate of the displacement $\dot{u}_i^0(\mathbf{x})$ can be obtained. Then, $\dot{u}_i^1(\mathbf{y})$ is also obtained by Eqn 16.

The rate of the second Piola-Kirchhoff stress of the global structure is described by Eqn 21. Because the homogenized elastic tensor C_{ijkl}^H is not symmetric w.r.t. k and ℓ , the rate of the second Piola-Kirchhoff stress of the macroscopic model can't be written in the same form as the one of the microscopic model defined by Eqn 13.

$$\dot{S}_{ij}^{macro} = C_{ijkl}^H \frac{\partial \dot{u}_k^0(\mathbf{x})}{\partial X_\ell} \quad (21)$$

NUMERICAL ANALYSIS

Using a computer program developed on the basis of the above formulation, we analyze the mechanical behaviors of composite materials under large deformation. Two finite element models, i.e., microstructure model and macrostructure model, are used in the simulation. Fig.4 explains it for an example of knitted fabric composite material. By homogenizing the microstructure at each time step, the macroscopic mechanical properties are calculated at each step. Then, using the updated homogenized mechanical properties, macroscopic deformation is calculated. That is to say, both the microscopic and macroscopic models are updated in every step. In this paper, we show the computational results for the unidirectional fiber reinforced plastics as in Fig.5. Fig.5 (a) shows the fiber-matrix model, and Fig.5 (b) shows only the fiber model. The fiber and matrix are assumed to be elastic and isotropic. The fiber volume fraction is about 50%. The mechanical properties of fiber and matrix used in the numerical analysis are shown in Table 1. The analysis for the following three cases are carried out as shown in Fig.6.

- (i)Tensile deformation in the transverse direction to the fibers
- (ii)In-plane shearing deformation on the fibers cross section
- (iii)Out-plane shearing deformation on the fibers cross section

Table 1: The mechanical properties of fiber and matrix

	Fiber	Matrix
Young's modulus (MPa)	7300	150
Poisson's ratio	0.3	0.3

The results of analyses for the deformation of microscopic structure are shown in Fig.7 about case (i), Fig.8 about case (ii), and Fig.9 about case (iii). Concerning uniform tensile deformation, only the matrix is deformed but the fiber is hardly deformed. Concerning in-plane

Fig. 4: Schematic view of the macro-and microscopic modeling by the homogenization method

Fig. 5: Finite element model of the unit cell of the uni-directional fiber reinforced plastics

Fig. 6: Macroscopic boundary conditions

Fig. 7: Tensile deformation in the transvers direction to the fibers

Fig. 8: In-plane shearing deformation on the fibers cross section

Fig. 9: Out-plane shearing deformation on the fibers cross section

shearing deformation, the fiber is rotated without deformation by the macroscopic pure shearing deformation, then the matrix is deformed. Concerning out-plane shearing deformation, the cross section of the fiber is inclined without deformation and the surface of the microstructure is waved.

CONCLUSION

The purpose of this study was to analyze the mechanical behaviors of composite materials under the large deformation by the homogenization method. First, we discussed on the periodicity of the microstructure after large deformation from experimental work for knitted fabric composite material. It was found that the periodicity remains locally enough to apply the homogenization formulation. Next, the formulation of the homogenization method applied to large deformation problem was described. In this formulation, the displacements of both

macroscopic model and microscopic model were defined precisely. Finally, using the developed program based on this formulation, the numerical analysis for the unidirectional fiber reinforced plastics was carried out.

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